

The Impact of Serum Vitamin D Levels on the Prevalence of Musculoskeletal Disorders among Garment Workers in Bangladesh: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

MSD is a very important issue among the garments worker because it creates health problem like MSD in upper and lower part of the body, increase sick leave and absenteeism and decrease productivity which ultimately makes a great impact of our total economy. The Cross-sectional study was carried out to determine the serum Vitamin D level and status of MSD among the garments worker at selected garments industries (Classic Shirts Ltd.) in Bangladesh. The serum Vitamin D level was measured by ELISA method. The total 168 respondents were included in this study where 64.3% respondents were Female and 35% were Male respondents with the mean age was 27.42 ± 7.484 years. Among the respondents 13.7% were illiterate whereas 45.2% were Primary level and 41.1% completed their high school or secondary level education. Among the respondents 61.3% were unmarried and 80.4% belongs to nuclear family. Their mean work experience 4.52 ± 2.153 years and mean monthly income was 7376.88 ± 6.302 tk BDT. Among the respondents 67.3% work in standing position whereas 32.7% is in sitting position. Moreover, 10.1% worked in cutting section whereas 64.3% worked in sewing section followed by 13.1% worked in finishing section and 12.5% respondents worked in ironing section. Among the respondents 62.5% had previous work experience and 63.4% were from same profession. In these participants group, about 86.3% participants had sufficient Vitamin D level with mean serum Vitamin D 70.37 ± 8.838 ng/ml and 61.3% had normal BMI with mean BMI 22.75 ± 3.535 kg/m². Out of 168 respondents the total 35.1% reported of MSD in different area of body where 67.8% respondents were in standing posture and 32.2% in sitting posture and it has found that, the number of MSD is higher among the participants who are working in standing position ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, it has also recorded that, the Number of MSD is high among the participants who have long time work experience ($p < 0.05$). From this study a significant association has found between serum vitamin D level and MSD. Those participants who had insufficient or deficient level serum vitamin D 23.7% were suffering from MSDs and 8.3% had

no MSDs. Here test of significant value is <0.05 which indicates sufficient level of serum Vitamin D can reduce the prevalence of developing MSDs. It was also observed that, among the respondents who were sufferings from MSD, whom 18.6% had both insufficient Vitamin D level and positive family history and 37.5% had no MSDs in spite of having insufficient Vitamin D level and negative family history. On the other hand, 81.4% had MSDs although they had sufficient level of vitamin D but had positive family history. At the same time, 94.4% respondents had no MSD though they had positive family history but they had sufficient level of Vitamin D. According to statistics I found that if serum vitamin D increases 1 unit, number of MSD can be decreased in one person per four persons.

Keywords: Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), Serum Vitamin D levels, Garment workers, Bangladesh, Cross-sectional study, Occupational health, Ergonomics, Work-related fatigue, Standing posture, Sewing section workers, Body Mass Index (BMI), Pain assessment, ELISA method, Workplace hazards, Nutritional deficiency, Female workforce, Occupational diseases, MSD prevalence, Vitamin D deficiency, Chronic pain

Introduction

Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are injuries or pain in the musculoskeletal system which affects the human body's movement. The MSDs includes pain in the joints, ligaments, muscles, nerves, tendons, and structures that support limbs, neck and back. When a person is exposed to MSDs risk factors, they begin to fatigue. When fatigue spread out in their body's recovery system, they start to develop musculoskeletal imbalance. So, when fatigue continues to increase and musculoskeletal imbalance persists, that ultimately leads to progress of musculoskeletal disorders. (Musculoskeletal disorders program; 24.3.2016)

Musculoskeletal disorder is the second most common reason for visits to physician. ^[1] It also a major cause of activity limitation and work absence throughout the world. ^[2] .It was recorded in a previous study that, those who works in standing position for a long time specially the female workers having more experience in both subjective and physical fatigability. ^[3]

There are many causes of MSDs and occupational hazard is one of them. There are many working area where workers have to maintain the same posture over a prolong period of time and often several years. Even sometimes natural postures like standing can lead to MSDs like low back pain. But postures which are unnatural like twisting or tension in the upper or lower body are typically contributors to the development of MSDs because of the unnatural biomechanical load of these postures. (Musculoskeletal disorders and workplace factors; 24.3.2016)

In 1997, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's (CDC) National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) released a review statement for work-related MSDs. According to that statement, some work conditions like routine lifting of heavy objects, daily exposure to whole body vibration, work with the neck in chronic flexion position, or performing repetitive forceful tasks has reported positive evidence for relationships between work conditions and developing MSDs of the neck, shoulder, elbow, hand and wrist, and back. ^[4]

On the other hand, a study has showed that, vitamin D plays a central role in the musculoskeletal system. Vitamin D is a fat soluble vitamin, which produce endogenously in our body in exposure to sun-light and is well known for multiple functions in bone biology, autoimmune diseases, cell growth, inflammation or neuromuscular and other

immune functions. It has been proven in many studies that, vitamin D deficiency causes many diseases. In cases of vitamin D deficiency, there has found a strong negative impact on bone health like, rickets, osteomalacia, osteopenia, primary and secondary osteoporosis and musculoskeletal pain. ^[5]

Vitamin D has immunomodulatory activities. Deficiency of vitamin D might be associated with diseases of immune dysregulation, which can be manifested by excessive daytime sleepiness, fatigue, tiredness, non-specific musculoskeletal pain. ^[6]

Again, a study showed, the prevalence of low vitamin D is high in patients who present with fatigue and stable chronic medical conditions. After normalization of vitamin D levels with ergocalciferol therapy significantly improves the severity of their fatigue symptoms. In that study, the prevalence of low vitamin D was 77.2% in patients who presented with fatigue. After normalization of vitamin D levels fatigue symptom scores improved significantly ($P < 0.001$) in all five subscale categories of fatigue. ^[7]

On the contrary, A cross-sectional and interventional study was carried out in two phase in which, complaints of unexplained pain in upper and lower limbs were noted among senior executives of some companies who worked long hours in air-conditioned offices and in spite of living in a city with a tropical climate, were barely exposed to sunlight. In the first phase of that study, after assessing other causes and serum vitamin D3 level, the result has revealed that, the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency is lower (25%) in those who give history of regular exercise in open air than in others (46.2%) and vitamin D deficiency is higher (47%) in those whose workday started earlier than in those whose workday started later (12%). In the second phase of that study, significant improvements were seen in unexplained pain in upper and lower limbs and serum D3 values after 3months sun exposure, oral therapy and dietary modifications. ^[8]

Bangladesh is a developing and highly populated country of 147610 km² with a population of nearly 160 million. Garment manufacturing is the biggest industrial sector of Bangladesh. The total number of garment workers is 1.6 million, among which 80% are women and most of them almost 70% or 80% workers are young girls. They are very hard working and their life is full of struggle. They mostly seen in the Dhaka city, coming from different areas of the country. They work from 8 am. to 8 pm during which they are not getting chance to come in sun-light exposure. So, there is a chance of Vitamin D deficiency which may be a cause of MSD among the garments workers.(Life of a garments worker in Bangladesh, 2017)

The health and well-being of working people and their families are greatly influenced by the quality of their work environments, which is a direct result from exposures to physical hazards on the job and risks associated with the organizational context, or indirectly through the impact of work on health behaviors. ^[9]

The proposed study is an attempt to find out whether there is any association between statuses of vitamin D and development of musculo-skeletal disorders among Bangladeshi garments workers.

BACKGROUND

Vitamin D is the latest trend in the news at the moment. Recently the NHS in the UK announced that increasing vitamin D intake, especially in the winter months can help prevent millions of colds and flu cases and possibly save lives. (Add vitamin D to food to prevent colds and flu; 2017)

A recent study found out that, in places where sunshine is not common, the people of those places are suffering from some underlying health conditions such as cancer, diabetes, high blood pressure, poor semen quality, depression, osteoporosis, fatigue, depression etc. There seems to be no limit to the illnesses that vitamin D can affect. Even though knowledge connecting low levels of vitamin D with severe health issues is available, people are still getting far too little of the vital vitamins. (We are not getting enough Vitamin D; 2014)

Vitamin D is sometimes called the “sunshine vitamin” because it’s produced in your skin in response to sunlight. Our body produces vitamin D naturally when it’s directly exposed to sunlight. Vitamin D has several important functions such as absorption of calcium, phosphorus, and facilitating normal immune-system function. Getting a sufficient amount of vitamin D is important for normal growth and development of bones and teeth, and improved resistance against certain diseases. (Benefits of Vitamin D; the sunshine Vitamin; 2017)

Vitamin D refers to a group of fat-soluble vitamins which play an important role for increasing intestinal absorption of some micro-nutrients such as calcium, magnesium, phosphate and multiple other biological effects. In humans, the most important compounds in this group are vitamin D₃ (also known as cholecalciferol) and vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol). ^[10]

Vitamin D isn't found in many foods, the major natural source of the vitamin is synthesis of cholecalciferol in the skin from cholesterol through a chemical reaction that is dependent on sun exposure specifically UVB radiation. Vitamin D from the diet or skin synthesis is biologically inactive; a reaction process named hydroxylation which is also known as enzymatic conversion is needed and for this whole activation process liver and kidney is compulsory. Cholecalciferol is converted in the liver to 25-hydroxycholecalciferol and ergocalciferol is converted to 25-hydroxyergocalciferol. These two vitamin D metabolites are also called as 25-hydroxyvitamin D or 25(OH)D. These 25(OH)D are measured in serum to determine a person's vitamin D status. Calcitriol is further hydroxylated by the kidneys to form calcitriol, which is the biologically active form of vitamin D and also known as 1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol. ^[11]

Vitamin D: Sources

Sun exposure

Sunlight is considered as the main source of vitamin D for human population. ^[12] Irradiation of ultraviolet (UV) B of wavelength of 290–320 nanometers enters in skin and converts cutaneous 7-dehydrocholesterol to pre-vitamin D₃, which in turn becomes vitamin D₃. UV radiation exposure and vitamin D synthesis may be affected by season, day duration, cloud, smog, skin melanin content, and sunscreen. (Dietary reference Intakes for Calcium and Vitamin D; 2010). Gloomy environment can reduce 50% of UV energy and 60% reduced by greenhouse gases (Wharton B.; et al; 2003). UV radiation cannot cross transparent glass, so sunshine entering through window cannot produce vitamin D ^[13] Developing general guidelines for UV radiation and sun exposure in maintaining adequate vitamin D levels is

sometimes very difficult. Researchers suggest that sun exposure for approximately 5–30 minutes in peak day time for minimum twice a week to the body surface without using any sunscreen is usually sufficient for vitamin D synthesis. ^[14]

Individuals and women who generally wear long robes and cover head for either religious or occupation purposes limit themselves to sun exposure to obtain adequate vitamin D. ^[14,15]

Food

Vitamin D is available only in small number of natural foods. The Cod liver oil (400-1000 IU/ml), salmon fish (600-1000 IU) and tuna fish (236 IU) are the best sources of vitamin D. Vitamin D is also available in beef liver, milk (100 IU/ml), cheese(100IU/ml) and egg yolks (20 IU/ml) is very little amounts. ^[16] Variable amounts of vitamin D₂ are also provide in some mushrooms (1600 IU). ^[17]

Dietary supplements

Some supplements and fortified foods may provide the two forms of Vitamin D; D₂ (ergocalciferol) and D₃ (cholecalciferol). Vitamin D₂ is manufactured by the UV irradiation of ergosterol in yeast, and vitamin D₃ is manufactured by the irradiation of 7-dehydrocholesterol from lanolin and the chemical conversion of cholesterol. ^[18] So the researchers should take an attempt to find out whether there is any association between development of fatigability and statuses of vitamin D among Bangladeshi garments workers.

Research Question

What is the status of serum Vitamin D and musculoskeletal disorders among the garments workers in Bangladesh?

Problem Statement

Bangladesh is a densely populated country and recently has promoted as middle income country. Most of populations (especially in Dhaka city) are garments worker and they work from morning 8.00am to 8.00pm of evening. Whenever they do the overtime duty they work till 9.00pm to 10.00pm at night. That's why the garments workers don't get enough opportunity for sun exposure and vitamin D deficiency is now the evidence of lifestyle disorder in population. Most of the garments workers are suffering from fatigability specially musculoskeletal disorders which may be an outcome of vitamin D deficiency.

Justification

In Bangladesh, approximately 4million of total population are working in readymade garments sector of which 80% are female. (BGME report; September, 2018) Studies reported that, most of them suffers from some sorts of fatigability specially due to musculoskeletal disorders such as low back pain, knee joint pain, ankle joint pain, pain in the muscles of lower limbs etc. which reducing their working capacity ultimately great loss of productivity.

Scientists discovered that deficiency of serum vitamin D might be the cause of muscular weakness and muscle pain among adults. In human body, around 90% vitamin D generally derived from sunlight and rest from dietary intake. Both physical and environmental factors may affect individual's exposure to sun light and thus limit the ability of

production of vitamin D endogenously within their body. Deficiency of vitamin D is now a days been identified as the evidence of life style disorder in the urban population even after abundant sunlight. They fail to expose themselves to sunlight due to long working time, lack of physical activities and exercises. Researchers suggest that sun exposure for approximately 5-30 minutes in peak day time for minimum twice a week to body surface without using any sunscreen is usually sufficient for vitamin D synthesis. Individuals and women who wear long robes and cover head or either religious or occupational purpose limit themselves to sun exposure to obtain adequate vitamin D.

As it is observed that the garments worker in Bangladesh have to work more than 12hours long time in indoor area which is devoid of sun exposure may develop the vitamin D deficiency and also may responsible for develop fatigability among them. So occupational health scientists should look after this issue to investigate the association between vitamin D deficiency and developing musculoskeletal problems among the garments workers.

Objectives

General Objectives:

- To estimate the status of serum Vitamin D level and determine Musculoskeletal Disorders among the Garments workers.

Specific Objectives:

- To determine Musculoskeletal disorders among the Garments workers
- To estimate the status of serum Vitamin D level among the respondents
- To find out the relationship between serum Vitamin D level and MSDs among the garments workers.
- To find out the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondent

List of Variables:

Socio-economic Demography:

- Age
- Sex
- Educational level
- Family History of MSD
- Living area
- Income

Work-Related Factors:

- Type of work
- Working posture
- Working Hour
- Pervious work history

Pain related:

- Site of pain
- Type of pain
- Duration of pain
- Aggravating factors of pain
- Relieving factors of pain
- Functional disabilities due to pain

Sun exposure

- Time and frequency of sun exposure
- Body surface that exposed to sun
- Lunch time activities

Food Habit:

- Milk
- Yogurt
- Egg
- Tuna Fish

Affected sites of musculoskeletal disorders:

- Discomfort in neck
- Discomfort in shoulder joint
- Discomfort in lower part of back
- Discomfort in Hip joint
- Discomfort in knee joint
- Discomfort in inter-phalangeal joint (Both upper & lower limbs)

Biochemical parameters of subject

- Serum Vitamin D
- Serum to measure rheumatoid factors antibody

Conceptual Frame-work:

Literature Review

Bangladesh is a developing country. Once upon a time her economic development was fully depended on agriculture. Now Bangladesh is one of the world's leading clothing exporters, and there are about 4500 garments factories in which approximately 3.6million people are working. ^[19]

Like other developing countries, Bangladesh is facing some occupational health problems in garments industries which is relating to communicable diseases, malnutrition, deficiency diseases and causing sufferings for the workers which is an important cause for absenteeism and is a major concern among owners of the factories and policy makers. ^[20]

Different steps have been taken to improve the both workplace conditions and health of the workers. But still, the conditions of the garment factories are unsafe and workers are at risk of developing different illnesses like respiratory problem, eye problem, muscle pain, headache, work related stress, low back pain, fatigability etc. ^[21]

The garments workers have to perform only one function or movement for a long period of time or day after day. The workers may have experience due to long hours sitting or standing any of the following: muscle fatigue, dizziness and body tiredness, numbness in fingers, numbness in thighs, difficulty moving finger, stiff joints, or back pain and the most frequently affected areas of the body are the arms and the back. Working in both sitting and

standing position may need more mobility large degree of freedom. Meanwhile when the standing worker spent a long period of time in standing position throughout their working hours, they may feel discomfort and experienced muscle fatigue at the end of workday and in the long terms, they will potentially experience occupational injuries. It is well known that prolonged standing has been linked to the onset of work-related musculoskeletal disorders associated with lower back pain among industrial workers. ^[22]

One study has found that increased discomfort and whole body fatigue associated with prolonged standing causes localized muscle fatigue and commonly represented as foot and lower leg swelling. On the other hand duration of the working hours is another trigger to increase the MSD related health problems of the standing workers. According to A. Magora (1972), workers perform jobs in standing position for more than 4 hours each day, they will potentially exposed to WMSD (Work related musculoskeletal disorder) associated with lower back pain. On the other hand one recent study reported that around 50 percent of healthy respondents reported discomfort in the lower back, even though exposed after 2 hours of continuous standing. ^[23]

We know that, the main source of Vitamin D is sunlight. Bangladesh has a tropical monsoon climate characterized by wide seasonal variations in rainfall, high temperatures, and high humidity. Regional climatic differences in this flat country are minor. Three seasons are generally recognized: a hot, muggy summer from March to June; a hot, humid and rainy monsoon season from June to November; and a warm-hot, dry winter from December to February. In general, maximum summer temperatures range between 38 and 41 °C (100.4 and 105.8 °F). April is the hottest month in most parts of the country. January is the coolest month, when the average temperature for most of the country is 16–20 °C (61–68 °F) during the day. (Geographical location of Bangladesh.; 2011)

So, Bangladesh gets enough sun exposure by which normal vitamin D level can be maintain. But the garments workers have to work from morning to evening and don't get enough opportunity of sun exposure. According to a study, about 90% of garments workers are suffering from fatigability specially fatigability. Standing and female workers are the most vulnerable group. ^[24]

Bangladesh is a developing country. Once up on a time her economic development was fully depended on agriculture. Although Bangladesh is not developed in industry, but now her economic has started to depend on industry and it has been enriched in Garment industries in the recent past years. In the field of Industrialization garment industry is a promising step. It has given the opportunity of employment to millions of unemployed, especially innumerable uneducated women of the country. It is making significant contribution in the field of our export income. For these Garments industries Bangladesh has got recognition as a middle income country in the world. ^[25]

Bangladesh readymade garments (RMG) sector is one of the fastest growing sectors in the Bangladeshi economy, rather than other industries. These garments industries have a great contribution in our economy with 55% growth rate 2002-2012. (Role of readymade garment sector in economic development of Bangladesh.; 2014)

The readymade garments industry acts as a stimulant for the development of Bangladesh. The industry that has been making vital contribution to reconstructing the country and its economy is none other than the readymade garment (RMG) industry which is now the single biggest export earner for Bangladesh. The sector accounts for 81% of total

export earnings of the country. When our only major export earner "the jute industry" started losing its golden days, it is the RMG sector that replaced it, and then, to overtake it. The "Made in Bangladesh" tag has also brought glory for the country, making it a prestigious brand across the globe. The country with its limited resources has been maintaining 6% annual average GDP growth rate and has brought about remarkable social and human development. (Bangladesh Garments Manufacturers and Exporters Association.; 2015)

The garment industry employs about 4.5 million workers, of whom about 80% are women. Bangladesh is one of the leading exporters of ready-made garments (RMG) worldwide and thus this sector provides the height contribution for broadening the economy of Bangladesh. ^[26]

For these reason various steps has taken to help the garments worker for keeping physically, mentally, socially healthy. But a study on garments worker revealed that still, the garments worker were suffering from a number of general and work- related diseases despite taking various measures to provide a safe and healthy life. A study was done over a garments worker of savar, and a different result has come out from that study about the health status of the garments worker. The result of that study was, "the average BMI of the male and female respondents was 21.4 ± 3.8 and 19.5 ± 3.4 respectively. About 27% of the workers were in under-nutrition state ($BMI < 18$) and this was more common to the female (32.1%) respondents. The common physical hazards perceived by the workers were dust (44.5%), overcrowding (40.5%), poor ventilation (39.9%), excess heat (39.6%), and noise (35.2%). Overall, the ergonomic hazards, particularly the awkward posture (58.1%) was perceived more by the workers. Comparatively, a higher proportion of workers of Savar garment factory which was situated in a rented building perceived both physical and ergonomic hazards. The general illnesses which were found to suffer commonly by the workers were respiratory problems (18.1%), headache (17.2%), fever (13.8%) and eye problems (11.2%). Regarding work-related diseases, the workers were found to suffer from musculoskeletal disorders (49.6%) and psychological illnesses (24.5%). The most common musculoskeletal disorders were low back pain (28.9%) and that of the psychological illnesses was sleep disturbance (16.4%)" ^[27]

Again, a study was carried out to explore the musculoskeletal disorders and the ergonomic factors amongst the workers of three garments factories which was situated is Mirpur, Tongi and Savar. In that study, about 57.5% were found to be suffering from some kind of musculoskeletal problems in different sites of their body among the total respondents and the problems were very common among the workers who worked in the sewing and finishing sections due to lack of ergonomical knowledge. Illiteracy, lack of knowledge about occupational diseases, poor ergonomic management, poor working environment, lack of facilities and low socio-economic condition were common in those industries. ^[28]

The way to measure vitamin D in our body is 25-hydroxy vitamin D blood test. The normal level of 25-hydroxy vitamin D is 20 nanograms/milliliter to 50 nanograms/mL is considered adequate for healthy people. A level less than 12 nanograms/mL indicates vitamin D deficiency. (Vitamin D Deficiency.; 2018)

On the other hand, a study suggested a positive relationship between Vitamin D deficiency and unexplained musculoskeletal pain, especially in older women. The studies presented the scenario in such a way like, the prevalence of musculoskeletal pain was 4.4% among the respondents with normal serum vitamin D, 4.9% in the group of mild vitamin D deficiency, 7.4% in the group of moderate vitamin D deficiency and 11.3% in the group

who has severe vitamin D deficiency. There was 95% relative risk for unexplained musculoskeletal pain of severe vitamin D deficiency. (Association between Vitamin D deficiency and unexplained musculoskeletal pain.;2018) Again, it was recorded in a study that, there is a potential relationship between low levels of 25-hydroxy vitamin D and a variety of chronic pain states. Sufficient levels of circulating vitamin D are necessary for absorption of other essential vitamins and minerals, particularly calcium, which plays a crucial role in promoting good bone and muscle health. Vitamin D also reduce inflammation, increase cell growth along with cellular activities, influences the immune and neuromuscular systems which plays a protective role against chronic pain. Insufficient and deficient vitamin D levels have been associated with a multiple poor health outcomes, including cardiovascular disease, hypertension type-II diabetes, cancer (e.g. colorectal, breast, prostate), autoimmune diseases (e.g. multiple sclerosis), inflammation, mood disorders/depression, cognitive function and Alzheimer's, as well as all-cause mortality. ^[29]

Vitamin D enhances the absorption of dietary calcium and phosphorus. Vitamin D promotes calcium absorption in the gut and maintains blood calcium levels to enable normal bone mineralization and prevent low blood calcium levels that can cause tetany. Vitamin D insufficiency leads to secondary hyperparathyroidism that causes increased bone loss, osteopenia, osteomalacia, osteoporosis and increase fracture risk. Again, every year, approximately one in three people in between 65 years to older experiences at least one fall, with 5.6% resulting in a fracture and vitamin D can play a role in reducing pain. There are vitamin D receptors in human muscle which effects directly on muscle strength. A severe vitamin D deficiency can cause myopathy, which results muscle weakness and pain. Vitamin D supplementation can reverse this and improve balance. Supplementing 700-1,000 IU/day of vitamin D3 has been shown to possibly reduce falls by 19%-26% and dosage greater than 800 IU/day given with calcium has been shown to lowers the risk of fracture by 10%-15%. Another advantage to correcting a vitamin D deficiency has been seen in decreasing knee and hip joint pain. ^[30]

Vitamin D deficiency can occur for a number of reasons, such as:

- Lack of sun exposure
- Darker skin
- Malabsorption
- Kidney fails to Activate Vitamin D
- Don't consume the recommended levels of the vitamin over time.
- Obesity.(www.webmd.com)

The common symptoms of Vitamin D deficiency include bone pain, muscle weakness, day time sleepiness, fatigue, lack of interest in the work, hypertension, always feeling discomfort and depression. While many factors can influence these symptoms, but such conditions may be signs of vitamin D2 or D3 deficiency.(Nancie Gorge. 5 illness linked to Vitamin D deficiency)

So, for providing physically, mentally and socially healthy life to garments worker and to increase garments productivity it is important to find out the relationship between developing fatigability and Vitamin D deficiency. So that we can take necessary steps to solve the problem which will help to make our economy more solvent.

METHODOLOGY

Study design

It is a cross sectional study

Sample size

A total 217 subject were estimated by using this Sample size was determined by using the formula

– Sample Size

$$n = z^2pq/d^2$$

where, n = desire sample size

z= the standard normal deviate usually set at 1.96 which correspondents to 95% confidence level.

p= Study by Amar Kapadia et al. found a prevalence of Vitamin D3 deficiency of 17.33% at Hazira in Inida.

q= 1-p and d = degree of accuracy desired, usually set at 0.05%

So the desired sample size would be = 217

Study Area: This study will be carried out of selected garments in Bangladesh

- **Study Period & Duration:** 1 year
- **Study Population:** Study population will be all garments industry workers having minimum work experience is two years.
- **Selection criteria of study population**

Inclusion criteria:

- Those who will be willing to give consent & participate in the study.
- Those who are working in garments factory (Minimum 2 years to 6years working in garments factory)
- Randomly.

Exclusion criteria:

- Those who will refuse to participate in the study.
- Any worker who will absent on the day of the data collection.

Sampling technique

Simple random sampling technique will be adopted. All the available subjects during the data collection period who will be fulfilled the study selection criteria will be included in the study.

Data collection instrument

- A semi-structured questionnaire and checklist using the selected variables according to the specific objectives.
- Checklist

- Blood collection tools (disposable syringe with needle, hand gloves, tourniquet, skin sterilizer, cotton, banded)
- Biochemical reagents.

Data collection technique:

- **SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC AND HEALTH-STATUS ASSESSMENT**

At the time of enrollment, trained research assistants will administer a pretested socio-demographic and pain relating questionnaire of each participating subject. Socio-demographic variables including age, household size, education of parents or caregiver, income, employment of the head of the households and housing condition will be recorded.

- **DETERMINATION OF PAIN**

Site, time and frequency of pain will be obtained along with family history of similar pain and the pain relieving methods using questionnaire.

Pain severity will be evaluated using Visual Analog Scale{VAS}, a linear scale where a score from 0 to 10 is marked according to the severity of pain. Respondents will be asked to mark the severity of pain they experienced during the last attack.

- **DETERMINATION OF SUN EXPOSURE**

Sun exposure history will be taken by interview whether the study participants stay outside especially when the sunlight is maximum (generally 10 am. to 4 pm). Participants will also be asked to record their primary activities during this specific time. Physical activity will be evaluated using questionnaire regarding type, frequency, and duration of each exercise. Sun exposure will assessed using questionnaire regarding the duration of exposure and the percentage of the body surface exposed.

- **BLOOD SAMPLE COLLECTION**

Venous blood will be collected in the morning taking by trained phlebotomist. Sample will be taken in the red-top tube for serum separator. Then the tubes will be kept in cold box and will send it to the reference laboratory within 4 h where Serum Vitamin D will be measured.

Collection OF Biological Sample

According to the Bangladesh Medical Research Council ethical guide line and permission will obtain from Bangladesh University of Health Sciences. After discussion with the respondents about the objectives and mode of data collection, will assure all the aseptic precaution and will also ensure all sorts of treatment if any complication arises during the process of biological sample collection and then taking prior written consent from the respondent of biological sample (venous blood) will be collected by following procedures:

- Blood pressure of the respondent will be check
- Will clean the desire skin area over the vein (anterior part of Elbow joint; frommedian cubital vein situated superficially over cubital fossa below superior radio-ulnar joint) with a liquid sterilizer (Hexisol)
- Will tie an elastic band (Tourniquet) around arm so the vein fills quickly with blood
- Will insert a small needle into the vein

- Will collect blood in a sterile 5cc syringe vial attached to the needle
- Will cover the puncture site with gauze and an adhesive bandage to stop any bleeding
- Will send the collected blood sample to a lab to measure serum Vitamin D level and RF antibody
- Every measurement will be ready for any emergency like bleeding, fainting etc.

DATA ANALYSIS

After collection, all the data will be checked and edited. Then data will be entered into computer with the help of software SPSS. Frequencies and rates along with means and standard deviations of almost all the variables will be measured. Association will also be statistically checked by appropriate test of significant.

Data collection method

- Socio-demographic and profession related information will be collected by face to face interview.
- Data will be conducted by structured and semi structured questionnaire.
- Questionnaire will be translated into local language to make more flexible to collect specific and precise data.

Ethical Consideration

- **Written consent :**
 - Approval from ethical review committee of the Bangladesh University of Health Science (BUHS).
 - Permission will be taken from Factory authority.
 - Privacy and confidentiality of the respondents will be maintained strictly.

Verbal consent :

- Consent form will be translated into local language.
- Verbal consent will be taken from each respondent before the interview

Result and Analysis:

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents according to age (n=168)

Age	Frequency	Percent
18-27year	109	64.9%
28-37years	44	26.2%
38-47years	15	8.9%
Total	168	100.0%

Mean 27.42±7.484 years. Minimum 18 years and maximum 47 years

(Table 1) shows distribution of respondents according to age; it was observed that more than one third 109 (64.9%) participants belonged to age 18-27 year, 44(26.2%) participants belonged to age 28-37 years, 15(8.9%) participants belongs to age 38-47 years.

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents according to sex (n=168)

(Table 2) shows distribution of the respondents according to sex; it was observed that, 64(35.7%) were male and 104(64.3%) were female.

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents according to educational status (n=168)

Education Level	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	23	13.7%
class 1 to 5	76	45.2%
class 6 to 10	69	41.1%

(Table 3) shows educational status of the respondents, it was observed that 23 (13.7%) participants were illiterate, 76(45.2%) participants had completed primary school education and 69 (41.1%) participants had completed secondary school certificate.

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents according to marital status (n=168)

Marital status	Frequency	Percent
married	65	38.7%
unmarried	103	61.3%
Total	168	100.0

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	64	35.7%
Female	104	64.3%
Total	168	100.0%

(Table 4) shows marital status of the respondents; it was reported that more than half 103 (61.3%) participants were unmarried and 65 (38.7%) were married.

Table 5: Distribution of the study participants according to family type (n=168)

Family type	Frequency	Percent
nuclear	135	80.4%
joint	33	19.6%

(Table 5) shows family type of the respondents, it was observed that more than two third 135 (80.4%) participants came from nuclear family and 33 (19.6%) participants came from joint family.

Table 6: Distribution of the study participants according to family members (n=168)

Family Member	Frequency	Percent
2 - 4	118	70.2%
5 - 7	39	23.2%
8 above	11	6.5%
Total	168	100.0%

(Table 6) shows family members of the respondents, it was observed that two third 118 (70.2%) participants had 2-4 members in their family, 39 (23.2%) participants had 5 - 7 members and 11 (6.5%) had 8 and above family members.

Table 7: Distribution of the study participants according to monthly family income (n=168)

Income	Frequency	Percent
5000 - 10000	103	61.3%
11000 - 15000	39	23.2%
16000 - 20000	18	10.7%
above 21000	8	4.8%

Mean monthly income was found 7376.88±6.302 tk

(Table 7) shows monthly income of the respondents; it was observed that more than half 103 (61.3%) participant's monthly income had 5000-10000 tk. 39(23.2%) participants monthly income had 11000 - 15000, 18(10.7%) participants monthly income had 16000- 20000 tk, 8(4.8%) participants monthly income had above 21000tk.

Table 8: Distribution of the study participants according to total working experience (n=168)

Total work experience	Frequency	Percent
2 – 5 years	133	79.2%
More then5 years	35	20.8%

Mean total work experience was found 4.52 ± 2.153 years

Table 8 shows working experience of the respondents, it was observed that 133 (79.2%) participant's working experience belonged to 2-5 years, 35 (20.8%) participant's work experience belonged more than 5 years.

Table 9: Distribution of the respondents by job section (n=168)

Section	Frequency	Percent
Cutting	17	10.1%
Swing	108	64.3%
finishing	22	13.1%
Ironing	21	12.5%

(Table 9) shows the distribution of the respondents by job section. It was observed that 17 (10.1%) were at cutting section, 108 (64.3%) participant's work was swing, 22(13.1%) participant's work was finishing section and 21 (12.5%) participant's work was ironing section.

Table 10: Distribution of the study participants according to working posture (n-168)

Working posture	Frequency	Percent
Sitting	55	32.7%
Standing	113	67.3%

(Table 10) shows the distribution of the respondents by working posture. It was observed that more than two third 113 (67.3%) participants work was standing posture, 55 (32.7%) participant's work was sitting posture.

Table 11: Distribution of the respondents according to previous work-experience (n-168)

Previous work experience	Frequency	Percent
yes	105	62.5%
no	63	37.5%

(Table 11) shows distribution of the respondents according to history of previous work experience, it was observed that more than two third 105 (62.5%) participants had previous work experience and 63 (37.5%) participants had no work experience.

Table 12: Distribution of the respondents by history of same profession in other organization (n=105)

History of same profession	Number	Percentage of case
Yes	64	63.4%
No	41	36.6%

* Multiple response

(Table 12) shows history of same profession in others organization of the study participants, it was observed that 109 (63.4%) participants had history of previous history of same profession and 63 (36.6%) had no history of same profession.

Table 13: Distribution of the respondents by Body Mass Index (n=168)

BMI	Frequency	Percent
Under weight	17	10.1%
Normal body weight	103	61.3%
Over weight	48	28.6%
Total	168	100.0%

Mean monthly BMI was found $22.75 \pm 3.535 \text{ kg/m}^2$

(Table 13) shows distribution of the respondents by Body Mass Index, it was observed that, one third participants 103 (61.3%) had normal body weight. 17 (10.1%) participants had less than normal body weight and 48 (28.6%) respondents had healthy BMI.

Table 14: Distribution of the study participants according to serum Vitamin D level (n=168)

Serum Vitamin D	Frequency	Percent
Insufficient/Deficient	23	13.7%
Sufficient	145	86.3%
Total	168	100.0%

Mean serum Vitamin D $70.37 \pm 8.838 \text{ ng/ml}$

(Table 14) shows distribution of the respondents according to serum Vitamin D level; it was observed that more than one third 145 (86.3%) participants had sufficient Vitamin D level, 23 (13.7%) participants had deficient or insufficient Vitamin D level.

Table 15: Distribution of respondents according to MSDs (n=168)

MSDs	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	59	35.1%
No	109	64.9%

(Table 15) shows history of body discomfort, it was observed that 109 (64.9%) participants had no body discomfort and 59 (35.1%) had MSDs.

Table 16: Distribution of the respondents by family history of MSD (n=168)

Family History of MSD	Frequency	Percent
yes	115	68.5%
no	53	31.5%
Total	168	100.0%

(Table 16) shows distribution of the respondents according to family history of MSDs, it was observed that more than two third 115 (68.5%) participants had previous family history of MSDs and 53 (31.5%) participants had no family history of MSDs.

Table 17: Distribution of the study participants according to number of sites involved MSDs (n=59)

Number of MSDs	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 site	32	0.54%
4-6 site	11	18.0%
Single site	22	37.0%

(Table 17) shows number of MSDs distribution of the study participants; it was observed that, 32(0.54%) participants had 1-3sites body discomfort, 11(18.0%) participants had 4-6sites involvement, 22 (37.0%) participants had single site of body discomfort and more than one-third respondents don't have body discomfort

Table 18: Distribution of the respondents according to site of MSDs (n=59)

Sites	Number	Percentage
Lower Back	39	60.0%
Shoulder	31	47.7%
Knee joint	24	36.9%
Hip Joint	17	26.2%
Neck	16	24.6%
Elbow Joint	16	24.6%

*

Multiple response

(Table 18) shows participants according to multiple response; it was reported that 16 (24.6%) participants had neck pain, 31(47.7%) participants had shoulder pain, 39(60.0%) participants had low back pain, 16 (24.6%) participants had elbow joint pain, 17 (26.2%) participants had hip joint pain, 24 (36.9%) participants had knee joint pain

Table 19: Association between Sex & developing MSD among the respondents (n=168)

SEX	Have MSDs	No MSDs
Male	20 (33.9%)	44(40.4%)
Female	39 (66.1%)	65 (59.6%)

$\chi^2 = 0.679$ p= 0.256

(Table 19) shows Association between Sex & MSDs among the respondents; it was observed that, 20 (33.9%) male had MSDs, where, 44 (40.4%) male had no MSDs. Again, 39 (66.1%) female had MSD, whereas 65 (59.6%) female had no MSDs. Statistically the association between Sex & developing MSD among the respondents were not significant (p>.05)

Table 20: Association between working posture & MSDs among the respondents (n=168)

Working posture	Have MSDs	NO MSDs
	Sitting	19(32.2%)

Standing	40 (67.8%)	69 (63.3%)
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$$\chi^2 = 5.301 \text{ p} = 0.021$$

(Table 20) shows Association between working posture & MSDs among the respondents; it was observed that, those participants who are working in standing position 40 (67.8%) had MSDs and those who are working in sitting position 19 (32.2%) had MSDs. The Association between working posture & MSDs among the respondents was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Statistically, the number of MSD is higher among the participants who are working in standing position.

Table 21: Association between Family History & MSDs among the respondents (n=168)

History of MSD	MSD of the respondents	
	Have MSD	No MSD
Yes	43(37.4%)	72(62.6%)
No	16(30.2%)	37(69.8%)

$$\chi^2 = 0.826 \text{ p} = 0.232$$

(Table 21) shows Association between Family History & MSDs among the respondents (n=168); it was observed that, those participants who had family history of MSD 43 (37.4%) suffering from MSD and 72 (62.6%) had no MSD. At the same time, who had no family history of MSD 16 (30.2%) participants are suffering from MSD and 37 (69.8%) had no MSD problem. Here, $p > 0.05$, so statistically there is no significant association between Family History & MSDs among the respondents.

Table 22: Association between Age & developing MSDs among the respondents (n=168)

MSDs	Age group		
	18-27year	28-37years	38-47years
Have MSDs	39(36.1%)	15 (33.3%)	5 (33.3%)
NO MSDs	70 (63.9%)	29 (66.7%)	10 (66.7%)

$$\chi^2 = 0.131 \text{ p} = 0.937$$

(Table 22) shows Association between age group and developing MSDs among the respondents; it was observed that, those participants who were from 18-27 years age group 39 (36.1%) had MSDs and 70 (63.9%) had no MSDs. Again, who were from 28-37 age group, 15 (33.3%) had MSDs and 29 (66.7%) had no MSDs. Moreover, those who belonged to 38-47 age group 5 (33.3%) had MSDs and 10 (66.7%) had no MSDs. The association between age and developing MSDs among the respondents is statistically not significant. ($p > 0.05$)

Table 23: Association between Total working experience & MSDs among the respondents (n=168)

MSDs	N	Mean working experience	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
yes	59	3.75	2.945	.383
no	109	2.86	1.566	.150

Independent Samples Test					
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	14.777	.000	2.541	166	.012
Equal variances not assumed			2.145	76.155	.035

(Table 23) shows Association between working experience & MSDs among the respondents; it was observed that, those who had MSDs, the mean working experience was 3.75 years and those who had no MSDs, the mean working experience was 2.86 years. The Association between Total working year & MSDs among the respondents was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The Number of MSD is high among the participants who have long time work experience.

Table 24: Association between BMI & MSDs among the respondents (n=168)

MSDs	BMI Group		
	Under weight	Normal weight	body Healthy
yes	12 (20.3%)	34 (57.6%)	13 (22.0%)
no	33 (30.3%)	51 (46.8%)	25 (22.9%)

$\chi^2 = 2.313$ $p = .315$

(Table 24) shows Association between BMI and developing MSD among the respondents; it was observed that, those participants who had underweight 33 (30.3%) had no MSDs and 12 (20.3%) had MSDs. Again, who normal body weight, 34 (57.6%) had MSDs and 51 (46.8%) had no MSDs. Moreover, those who were healthy 13 (22.0%)

had MSDs and 25 (22.9%) had no MSDs. The association between BMI and developing MSDs statistically was not significant. ($p > 0.05$)

Table 25: Association between developing of MSDs and serum Vitamin D level among the respondents (n=168)

MSDs among the respondents	Serum Vitamin D	
	Insufficient/Deficient	Sufficient
Yes	14 (23.7%)	45 (76.3%)
No	9 (8.3%)	100 (91.7%)

$$\chi^2 = 7.755 \text{ p} = .006$$

(Table 25) shows Association between serum vitamin D level and developing MSDs among the respondents; it was observed that, those participants who had insufficient or deficient level serum vitamin D 14 (23.7%) were suffering from MSDs and 8(8.3%) had no MSDs. At the same time, those who had sufficient level of serum vitamin D level 100 (91.7%) had no complain of MSDs and 45 (76.3%) complained MSDs. Here test of significant value is < 0.05 which indicates there is an association between developing of MSDs and serum Vitamin D level among the respondents. The sufficient level of Vitamin D can reduce the prevalence of developing MSDs.

$$\chi^2 = 7.755 \text{ p} = .006$$

Table 26: Association between serum Vitamin D level & Sex of the respondents (n=168)

Sex	Vitamin D	
	Insufficient	Sufficient
male	10 (15.6%)	54 (84.4%)
female	13 (12.5%)	91 (87.5%)

$$\chi^2 = .327; p = .362$$

(Table 26) shows Association between serum Vitamin D level & Sex of the respondents; it was observed that, 13 (12.5%) female participants and 10 (15.6%) male had insufficient serum vitamin D level. At the same time, 91 (87.5%) female and 54 (84.4%) male had sufficient level of serum Vitamin D. Association between serum Vitamin D level & Sex of the respondents statistically were non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 27: Association between Age & Vitamin D level of the respondents (n=168)

AGE	Serum Vitamin D	
	Insufficient/Deficient	Sufficient
18-27year	17 (73.9%)	91 (62.8%)
28-37years	3 (13.0%)	42 (29.0%)
38-47years	3 (13.0%)	12 (8.3%)

$$\chi^2 = 2.768; p = 0.251$$

(Table 27) shows Association between serum Vitamin D level & Age of the respondents; it was observed that, one third participants from the age group 18-27 years 91 (62.8%) had sufficient serum Vitamin D level and 17 (73.9%) had insufficient Vitamin D. Simultaneously, from the age group 28-37 years 42 (29.0%) had sufficient serum Vitamin D level and 3 (13.0%) had insufficient level of serum Vitamin D. On the Contrary, the respondents who are from 38-47 years age group, 12 (8.3%) had sufficient serum Vitamin D, 3 (13.7%) had insufficient Vitamin D level and 6 (20.0%) had serum Vitamin D more that 100ng/dl. Here, $p = 0.251$ which is > 0.05 and indicating there is no statistical association between serum Vitamin D level & Age of the respondents.

Table 28: Association between total working experience & serum Vitamin D level among the respondents (n=168)

Total Work experience	Serum Vitamin D	
	Insufficient/Deficient	Sufficient
2-5years	19 (82.6%)	114 (78.6%)

More than 5 years	4 (17.4%)	31(21.4%)
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$$\chi^2 = 0.191; p = 0.452$$

(Table 28) shows Association between total working experience & serum Vitamin D level among the respondents; it was observed that, those respondents who have 2-5years work experience 19 (82.6%) had insufficient level of vitamin D and 114 (78.6%) had sufficient level of vitamin D. Again, those who have more than 5years work experience, 4(17.4%) had insufficient level of vitamin D and 31(21.4%) had sufficient level of vitamin D.

Table 29: Association between BMI & Vitamin D level among the respondents (n=168)

BMI	Serum Vitamin D	
	Insufficient/Deficient	Sufficient
15-20 kg/m ² (Under weight)	4 (9.5%)	38 (90.5%)
21-25kg/m ² (Normal body weight)	11 (12.8%)	75 (87.2%)
26-30kg/m ² (Healthy)	8 (20.0%)	32 (80.0%)

$$\chi^2 = 8.33; p = 0.089$$

(Table 29) shows Association between BMI & Vitamin D level among the respondents; it was observed that, those participants who had underweight 38 (90.5%) sufficient level of serum Vitamin D. Again, who had normal body weight, 75 (87.2%) had sufficient level of serum vitamin D. Moreover, those who were healthy 32 (80.0%) had sufficient serum vitamin D level. Statistically there is no association between BMI & Vitamin D level among the respondents because the test of significance was >0.05.

Table 30: Association between Family history of MSDs & serum Vitamin D level among the respondents (n=168)

MSD	Family History		Vitamin D status	
			Insufficient/Deficient	Sufficient
Have MSDs	Family History	Yes	8 (18.6%)	35 (81.4%)
		No	6 (37.5%)	10 (62.5%)
No MSDs	Family History	Yes	4 (5.6%)	68 (94.4%)
		No	5 (13.5%)	32 (86.5%)

$$\text{Regression: } B = -.024; p = 0.000$$

(Table 30) shows the association among currently sufferings from MSD by the respondents, their family history of MSD and serum Vitamin D level. Among the respondents who were sufferings from MSD, 8 (18.6%) had both insufficient Vitamin D level and positive family history and 6 (37.5%) had no MSDs in spite of having insufficient

Vitamin D level and negative family history. On the other hand, 35 (81.4%) had MSDs although they had sufficient level of vitamin D but had positive family history. At the same time, 68 (94.4%) respondents had no MSD though they had positive family history but they had sufficient level of Vitamin D. According to statistics I found that if serum vitamin D increases 1 unit, number of MSD can be decreased in one person per four persons

DISCUSSION

Musculoskeletal disorder is a type of disease which affects the locomotor system – such as, muscles, bones, joints and associated tissues such as tendons and ligaments. Musculoskeletal disorders are one the leading contributor to disability worldwide, with low back pain being the single leading cause of disability globally. Now-a-days, musculoskeletal disorders are not just conditions of older age – they are prevalent across the life-course. (WHO, 2019) Recently in many study, it has found that, a major number of the garments workers are suffering from MSD. This study was a cross sectional study conducted among 168 garments workers to find out the level of serum vitamin D and the status of MSDs among the garments workers in Bangladesh. Data was collected from those who were willing to give blood from serum Vitamin D analysis along with questioner from 168 working employees. Due to unavailability of respondents and time constraints, only 168 workers were interviewed. Questionnaire was translated into Bengali language and explained them. 20 minutes orientation has been given to share the purpose of study and then started to fill up the questionnaire. A semi- structured interview questionnaire was used to find out the status of MSDs among the garments workers. MSD disorders are taken as pain. Vitamin D measured from serum by ELISA method.

The aim of this study is to determine the serum Vitamin D level and status of musculoskeletal disorders among the garment workers in Bangladesh. Two garment industries were selected for recruiting this study almost more than one third 64.9% belonged to age 18-27 year with mean age 27.42 ± 7.484 years. It was reported that over the past quarter century, women have joined the labor market specially in garments sector is increasing in numbers day by day. (World development report 2012). In 2004, there were 3480 factories that employed 1.8 million workers of which 1.5 million were women ^[31], which also reflected in this study where females were predominant (Female 64.3% & Male 35.7%). Here, among the respondents most of them were completed (45.2%) primary school education and 41.1% participants had completed secondary school certificate which also co-relate with a study done by Sultana S, 2017. At the same time, more than half (61.3%) participants were unmarried and about more than two third (80.4%) participants belongs to nuclear family. These findings match with a study findings done by Rahman, HM & Siddiqui, SA 2015 where 58% participants were unmarried and 76% respondents belongs to nuclear family. Among the participants in this study, 79.2% participant's working experience belonged to 2-5years, 20.8% participant's had work experience more than 5years where mean work experience is 4.52 ± 2.153 years. This findings reflects with the study done by Antle DM 2013 where 73.4% participants had more than 4years work experience. Moreover from this current study found that, 61.3% respondents monthly income BDT 5000-10000 TK with mean income 7376.88 ± 6.302 tk which also corresponds with the study finding **Kiron MI, 2015 where 58.9% participants monthly were 6000-10000 TK BDT.**

In this study it was recorded that, 10.1% respondents were from cutting section, 64.3% participant were working in swing section, 13.1% participant's was from finishing section and 12.5% participant's was from ironing section. Among 168 participants about two third 67.3% participants work was in standing posture and 32.7% participant's work was sitting posture. Both these finding related s with the result of a study done by Ferdous KJ, 2014 where 66% respondents worked at swing section and 69.6% participants worked in standing position. About two third 62.5% participants of this study had previous work experience and 37.5% participants had no work experience. This result also relates with the findings of Ferdous KJ, 2014, where 60% participants had previous work experience. It was also recorded that, more than half of respondents 63.4% had history of previous history of same profession which reflects of a findings of a study done by Rahman HM, 2016 (52% had previous work experience of same profession). Among the participants, one third participants 61.3% had normal body weight, 10.1% participants had less than normal body weight and 28.6% respondents had healthy BMI with mean BMI $22.75 \pm 3.535 \text{ kg/m}^2$. This BMI findings also corresponds with the findings of a study done by ^[32] where 64% participants had normal BMI.

In this study among the respondents 64.9% had no MSDs and 35.1% had MSDs. It was observed that, who had MSDs, 19.0% participants had 1-3sites body discomfort, 16.5% participants had 4-6sites involvement, 13.1% participants had single site of body discomfort and more than one-third respondents don't have body discomfort. More than half of the participants about 60.0% respondents complained about pain in lower back and 36.7% had pain in the knee joint and these percentage is supported on recent study, Banik, et al. 2015 found their study among respondents 36.7% had MSD problem in knee joint and 42.2% lower back. Statistically there is no significant association between Sex & developing MSD among the respondents ($p > .05$) which is quite resemble with a study by ^[33].

In that study Hooftman WE, et al. 2009 can not able to explain the gender difference in musculoskeletal symptoms among workers. But According to the finding of this study female are more vulnerable for developing MSD (66.1% female and 33.9% male had MSDs). These study findings reflect with the result done by Sultana S, 2014. According to finding of that study female are more vulnerable for developing MSD in neck 61%, Hands 62%, Upper back 63%, Lower back 67% and Leg 63% than male. But, statistically there is an association between working posture & MSDs among the respondents ($p < 0.05$). Statistically, the number of MSD is higher among the participants who are working in standing position (standing position 67.8% and sitting position 32.2%). At the same time it was also found that, statistically the Number of MSD is high among the participants who have long time work experience, which means, the association between Total working year & MSDs among the respondents was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Both these findings co-relate with a study findings done by AFM Sarwer, 2008 on garments workers. In that study, it was found that, prevalence of MSD associated to work-related awkward postures (71%) is very high, along with who has long term work experience due to faulty ergonomics technique (21%). In addition in this study it has also found that, the association between both in age and BMI and developing MSDs among the respondents is not significant. ($p > 0.05$) According to this study,

there is no association between family history of MSD and developing MSD among the respondents ($p>0.05$), though ^[33] has found parental chronic musculoskeletal pain is positively associated with risk of chronic musculoskeletal pain in their adult offspring. But it has seen that, 37.4% respondents had MSD along with positive family history. At the same time it has seen that, the association between BMI and developing MSDs statistically was not significant. ($p>0.05$) and ^[34] has found in his study that, Maintaining normal body weight may reduce the risk of chronic musculoskeletal pain in offspring of pain-afflicted parents and in this study one third participants 103 (61.3%) had normal body weight.

On the contrary, it has recorded in this study that, more than one third 86.3% participants had sufficient Vitamin D level, 13.7% participants had deficient or insufficient Vitamin D level {sufficient level of Vitamin D $>30\text{ng/dl}$ and insufficient or deficient level of Vitamin D $<30\text{ng/dl}$ }. ^[35] In this study, it has found that there is an association between developing of MSDs and serum Vitamin D level among the respondents. It was observed that, those participants who had insufficient or deficient level serum vitamin D 23.7% were suffering from MSDs and 8.3% had no MSDs. At the same time, those who had sufficient level of serum vitamin D level more than half 91.7% had no complain of MSDs and 76.3% complained MSDs. Here test of significant value is <0.05 . This result co-relate with previous many studies. Recently, ^[36] has found Vitamin D has biphasic effects on both musculoskeletal system and cardiovascular system. In his study it has recorded, Vitamin D deficiency causes abnormalities in calcium, phosphorous and bone metabolism that can lead to muscle weakness, osteomalacia and osteopenia, which favors the finding of this study. Furthermore, the association between serum Vitamin D level & Sex of the respondents statistically were non-significant ($p>0.05$). At the same time, Vitamin D has no association with in respective to age, sex and BMI. ($p>0.05$)

In this study, it was observed that, the respondents who were sufferings from MSD, 43% had family history of MSDs of whom 18.6% had both insufficient Vitamin D level and positive family history and 37.5% had no MSDs in spite of having insufficient Vitamin D level and negative family history. On the other hand, 81.4% had MSDs although they had sufficient level of vitamin D but had positive family history. At the same time, 94.4% respondents had no MSD though they had positive family history but they had sufficient level of Vitamin D. According to statistics I found that if serum vitamin D increases 1 unit, number of MSD can be decreased in one person per four persons.

CONCLUSION

Respondents were mostly female and within the age group of 18-27 years. Among them MSD was found at different site of the body where the percentage of MSD was higher the female workers than the male workers. Among the respondents who worked in standing position was reported higher percentage of MSD in different area of body than the respondents who worked in sitting position. I found that if serum vitamin D increases 1 unit, number of MSD can be decreased in one person per four persons. Besides this, Statistically MSD has strong association with Vitamin

D over family history of MSD. At the same time, it has also come to known that, MSD has association with both working posture and work experience.

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